

Rapid Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) with Ethyl- α -Isonitrosoacetoacetate

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Manuscript received 12 March 1973; accepted 27 June 1973

Chloroform solution of ethyl- α -isonitrosoacetoacetate extracts palladium(II) quantitatively from aqueous acid, except HCl. Chloroform extract shows maximum absorbance at 400 nm. At this wavelength Beer's law is obeyed over the range 0.1-20 μ g of palladium per ml. 5 μ g of Pd in 10 ml solution can be estimated with an accuracy of 5%.

ETHYL- α -isonitrosoacetoacetate (HEINA) reacts with iron(II) in slightly alkaline medium to produce blue colour, which has been utilized for the colorimetric determination of iron^{1,2}. However, its use in the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of other metals has not been reported. In the present investigation, the extraction of palladium(II) with HEINA has been studied under wide range of experimental conditions and the colour in chloroform extract has been utilized for spectrophotometric determination of traces of palladium.

Experimental

Apparatus : Radioactivity and pH were measured as reported earlier³. Absorbance measurements were taken on a Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer using 1 cm. silica cells.

Reagents : A.R. grade reagents and chemicals were used. All solutions and the stock solution of palladium were prepared as described elsewhere⁴. Ethyl- α -isonitrosoacetoacetate (HEINA) was prepared by following the procedure recommended by Adkins and Reeve⁵.

Radioisotopes were obtained from Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay (India).

Procedure for Extraction and Separation of Palladium : Aqueous solution containing 0.1 to 35 mg. of Pd and adjusted to required acidity with appropriate acid, was taken in a 50-ml. separatory funnel and equilibrated for 2 min with an equal volume (10 ml.) of solution of HEINA in organic solvent. The two phases were allowed to separate and Pd in each phase was determined by the α -furildioxime method⁶ or by measuring the activity of Pd¹⁰⁹ on a γ -ray spectrometer. The pH of the aqueous phase after extraction was measured. In the study of the effects of other ions, the solution containing the ion

of interest was added before the adjustment of the pH of the solution.

Radioactive tracers, whenever available, were used to follow the extraction of other ions. The values for the separation factors (S) were calculated from the relation.

$$S = \frac{\text{Extraction coefficient of palladium}}{\text{Extraction coefficient of other element}}$$

Procedure for Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium : To an aqueous solution containing 1 to 200 μ g of Pd in a 50-ml. separatory funnel, 2 ml. of 5 M acetic acid were added and the volume was made to 10 ml with distilled water. Palladium was extracted into chloroform by equilibrating the aqueous phase twice for 2 min with 5 ml of 1% solution of HEINA in chloroform. The combined chloroform extract was taken in a 10-ml measuring flask and made up to the mark with 1% HEINA in chloroform, if required. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 400 nm, using a reagent blank. The amount of palladium present was determined from a calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Extraction and Separation of Palladium : The results of extraction studies (Table 1) show that palladium can be quantitatively extracted by HEINA into chloroform from aqueous solution of pH 0-7.2, and from 0.1 to 1 M solutions of acetic acid and 1 M solutions of mineral acids, except HCl. The extraction from acid solution is rapid and independent of time of equilibration over the period of 1-30 min. Palladium can be back-extracted quantitatively into the aqueous phase by shaking chloroform extract twice with 5 ml of 1 N HCl.

The values of the extraction coefficient of palladium give the following order for the organic solvents used—Chloroform > benzene > nitrobenzene >

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION COEFFICIENTS OF PALLADIUM WITH HEINA INTO CHLOROFORM AS A FUNCTION OF pH AND ACIDITY

Total palladium taken — 1 mg.
Organic phase — 10 ml. of 1% HEINA in Chloroform.
Volume of aqueous phase—10 ml.

pH or acidity	Extraction Coefficient	% Extraction
0.0	362.9	99.7
0.5	551.5	99.82
1.5	643.0	99.85
2.0	652.8	99.85
2.5	671.4	99.85
3.0	632.5	99.85
4.9	207.0	99.70
6.6	138.0	99.30
7.2	42.5	97.70
10.0	1.4	58.00
11.5	0.0045	0.40
1.0M HCl	0.007	0.70
1.0M H ₂ SO ₄	352.0	99.70
1.0M NHO ₃	362.9	99.70
1.0M CH ₃ COOH	856.0	99.88
0.1M CH ₃ COOH	836.0	99.88
0.5M "	836.0	99.88
0.75M "	836.0	99.88
1.0M "	836.0	99.88
2.0M "	480.0	99.78
6.0M "	16.2	94.20

1,2-dichlorobenzene > *n*-amyl alcohol > octariol > methyl isobutyl ketone > carbon tetrachlo de > butanol isoamyl alcohol > amyl acetate > ethyl acetate > ether.

Salts such as K, Na, Mg, Ca, Ba, Ce, Hg and Al nitrates do not affect the extraction coefficient value appreciably.

The values for the separation factors (Table 2) indicate that palladium can be effectively separated from a number of elements by extraction with HEINA into chloroform.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION FACTORS FOR DIFFERENT IONS IN THE EXTRACTION OF Pd-HEINA INTO CHLOROFORM FROM 1M ACETIC ACID SOLUTIONS

Total palladium tken — 1 mg.
Volume of aqueous phase—10 ml.
Organic phase — 10 ml. of 1% HEINA in Chloroform.

Separation factor (greater than)	Ions
10 ⁸	Zn ²⁺ , aCo ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ .
10 ⁷	Mn ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , La ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Sc ³⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Zr ⁴⁺ , aSb ³⁺ , Tl ⁺ , Ir ⁴⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ .
10 ⁶	Pt ²⁺ , aCa ²⁺ , Ag ¹⁺ , P ⁵⁺ , aCs ¹⁺ , Ru ³⁺ .
10 ⁵	Se ⁴⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Re ⁷⁺ .
10 ⁴	Au ³⁺ , Os ⁴⁺ .

a—Carrier free.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium
The absorption spectrum of Pd-HEINA in chloroform showed an intense absorption peak at 400 nm. (Fig. 1); so the absorption measurements were taken

Conc. of Pd = $3.77 \times 10^{-5} M$.
Conc. of HEINA = 0.062M.
Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of [Δ] HEINA and [O] Pd-HEINA in Chloroform.

at this wavelength. At this wavelength the absorption due to the reagent is 0.008. The plot of absorbance against concentration of palladium gives a straight line in the range 0.1–20 μg per ml, indicating that Beer's law is obeyed. The molar absorptivity of the coloured species calculated on the basis of total palladium taken is 9460 l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 400 nm. The absorbance of the solution does not show any change up to 24 hr.

The effect of variation in the concentration of HEINA up to 2% was studied keeping other factors constant. 10 ml of 0.1% solution of HEINA in chloroform is sufficient for extraction and colour development with 100 μg of palladium. However, in the presence of 10 mg of other ions which interact with HEINA, it is necessary to use 10 ml of 1% solution of HEINA.

The following ions, when present to the extent of 10 mg do not interfere in the spectrophotometric determination of palladium. Co(II), U(VI), Mg(II), Th(IV), Ca(II), Ba(II), Mn(II), Ag(I), Cd(II), Ni(II), Se(IV), Ce(III), Cu(II), Zn(II), Hg(II), Mo(VI), Fe(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Be(II), Au(III), La(III), As(III), Os(IV), Ru(III), Pt(IV), Ir(III), Rh(III), phosphate, pyrophosphate, chloride, bromide, chlorate, bromate, iodate, nitrate, sulphate, persulphate, and acetate. The interference by the ions tabulated in Table 3 can be removed by using appropriate masking agents. Iodide and thiocyanate are required to be separated by precipitating with silver nitrate. Cyanide is removed by boiling with formaldehyde.

Nature of the Extracted Species : The composition of the extracted species has been determined by the method of substoichiometric extraction of Pd(II) with HEINA into chloroform from 1 M acetic acid solution. The substoichiometric extraction was carried out as follows : Increasing amounts of palladium chloride solution ($3 \times 10^{-2} M$) labelled with Pd¹⁰⁹ were taken in a series of separatory funnels.

TABLE 3—MASKING AGENTS REQUIRED TO SUPPRESS THE INTERFERENCE BY OTHER IONS

Interfering ions	Masking agents added
EDTA and Tartrate	Copper sulphate
Oxalate and Citrate	Sodium molybdate
Thiosulphate	Sodium molybdate + Hydrogen peroxide.
Sulphite and Chloride (> 30 mg.)	Mercuric nitrate.

Each solution was made 1 M with respect to acetic acid (total volume = 10 ml.) and equilibrated for two minutes with 10 ml of 6×10^{-3} M HEINA in chloroform. The activity of 5 ml portion of each

Precision, Accuracy and Sensitivity : The precision and accuracy of the spectrophotometric method were tested by analysing solutions containing known amounts of palladium. The average of ten determinations with 5 μ g of palladium in 10 ml solution is 4.98 μ g which varies between 4.73 μ g and 5.23 μ g at 95% confidence limit. 0.1 μ g of Pd in 1 ml solution gives an absorbance of 0.01. The sensitivity of the method can be increased by employing volume concentration technique.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the grant of Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (M.R.P.).

Fig. 2. Substoichiometric extraction of Pd-HEINA into Chloroform. Organic phase = 10 ml of 0.006M HEINA.

organic phase was measured. The plot of activity against initial amount of palladium is linear (Fig. 2) till the reagent is substoichiometric to the palladium. A sharp break occurs at Pd : HEINA ratio of 1 : 2, after which the amount of Pd(II) extracted remains constant. This experiment confirms that the time of 2 min for reaching extraction equilibrium is adequate. Studies by Job's continuous variation method also indicate that the coloured complex is formed by the reaction of Pd and HEINA in the ratio of 1 : 2.

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